

The Ability to Solve Number Pattern Story Problems Examined from Heuristics Strategies

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ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
Published Online: 30 October 2025	This research aims to determine and describe the ability to solve number pattern story problems studied from the heuristic strategy at SMP Kemala Bhayangkari 1 Kubu Raya. The research method used is descriptive with an exploratory form. The subjects in this study were 36 students of class VIIIA. The data collection techniques for this study were written tests and interviews. This study is strengthened by the findings found in previous studies. Problem-solving abilities in number pattern story problems were studied using 4 stages from Polya, namely understanding the problem, planning a solution, carrying out the solution plan, and re-checking the results of the problem solving. The results showed that in solving mathematical problems students were divided into three categories of high, medium and low problem-solving abilities and students with high problem-solving abilities were able to fulfill all indicators in solving problems optimally, students with medium and low problem-solving abilities were less than optimal in completing the stages of solving number pattern story problems.
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I. INTRODUCTION

The world of education is inextricably linked to school mathematics. Mathematics is applied as a means to solve problems in other subjects and in work and everyday life. Formally, mathematics lessons are given to students starting in elementary school (SD), with the goal of preparing them to face an ever-evolving life through logical, rational, critical, careful, and honest thinking acquired through the educational process. From the perspective of the competencies to be achieved, mathematics emphasizes conceptual understanding, reasoning abilities, and problem-solving skills. Learning to solve problems is the primary goal of studying mathematics, because problem solving is an aspect of life that students definitely face, students abilities can be trained by frequently being given irregular practice questions (Akbar, et al, 2023). Problem solving plays a vital role in mathematics education, from elementary to secondary school. However, knowing how to incorporate problem solving comprehensively into the mathematics curriculum remains challenging for mathematics teachers. NCTM (2010) adds that the term problem solving refers to mathematical tasks that have the potential to provide intellectual challenge and enhance students' mathematical development.

The importance of problem-solving skills was put forward by Branca (Effendi, 2012) who said that problem-solving skills are the heart of mathematics. Furthermore, Russefendi (Effendi, 2012) also stated that problem-solving skills are very important in mathematics, not only for those who will later study or deepen their knowledge of mathematics, but also for those who will apply it in other fields of study in everyday life. Soedjadi in Bambang (2002) said that the problem-solving learning model requires teachers to prepare appropriate problems for students at a certain level. This model can also be arranged if students face large or complex problems, which are then directed to find certain concepts or principles, thus in the problem-solving process students are still guided by the teacher.

The importance of problem solving skills was also put forward by Hudojo (2005) who stated that problem solving is an essential thing in learning mathematics at school, because among other things: (1) students become skilled at selecting relevant information, then analyzing it and then researching the results; (2) intellectual satisfaction will arise from within, which is an intrinsic problem; (3) students' intellectual potential increases; (4) students learn how to make discoveries through the process of doing discovery.

“The Ability to Solve Number Pattern Story Problems Examined from Heuristics Strategies”

George Polya is a key figure in problem-solving theory (Sugiantara, et al., 2014). According to Polya, there are four indicators of problem-solving: understanding the problem, planning the solution, implementing the solution, and reviewing it (Brijlall, 2015). In working on problem-solving questions based on Polya's theory, students can connect the questions presented with events they have experienced, so that students do not only use their memory skills (Anwar, 2013). Based on the opinions above, it's only natural that problem-solving skills receive special attention, given their strategic role in developing students' cognitive potential, particularly in mathematics learning. However, the reality on the ground shows that students are not yet able to solve problems effectively, resulting in mathematics learning outcomes that fall short of expectations.

The low mathematical problem-solving ability of students deserves more attention from teachers. One of the studies that shows the low mathematical problem-solving ability of students is the results of Hanifah's (2020) research in class VIII of SMP Islam Bawari Pontianak, which shows that students' mathematical problem-solving ability on the set material is still relatively low, namely around 60% of 32 class VIII B students cannot solve mathematical problems well. A similar thing also happened when researchers gave Pre- Test questions to class VIII A students at SMP Kemala Bhayangkari 1 Kubu Raya, where students had very poor problem-solving abilities. Students were unable to understand the questions and were unable to solve the questions correctly and accurately. The following are students' answers to the questions presented:

1. $U_n = a + (n-1)b$
 $U_n = 9(2-36) - (a-36)$
 $= -72 - 1296 + 4$
 $= -1224 + 4$
 $= -122$

Figure 1. Student Problem Solving Results

5. Dik : Pada sebuah gedung bioskop, banyaknya kursi pada baris paling depan adalah 15 buah, banyak kursi dibelakangnya selalu lebih banyak kursi dari baris didepannya.
Ditanya : Maka banyak kursi pada baris ke-12 adalah ...
Jawab : $U_n = a + (n-1)b$
 $U_{12} = 15 + (12-1)2$
 $= 3$

Figure 2. Student Completion Result

Based on Figure 1.2 above, it can be seen from the answer sheet that students are only able to rewrite what is known and asked in the question but are unable to solve the problem accurately and correctly. This is also supported by the results of an interview with one of the eighth grade students who stated that they still have difficulty in solving math problems, especially math problems presented in story form. Students have not been able to solve the math problems given by the

teacher on their own, especially if the problems are given in the form of story problems. This is also in line with the results of an interview with the eighth-grade mathematics teacher who stated that students' understanding abilities are still very lacking, 80% of the 36 students still have great difficulty in solving math problems.

According to Manah (2016) the ability to solve mathematical problems based on Polya's stages for upper group students can carry out the Polya stages well, while for middle group students cannot carry out the Polya stages completely, and for lower group students cannot carry out the Polya stages completely. One strategy for solving mathematical problems is to provide guides that can direct students towards solving problems called Heuristic strategies. This strategy relies on efforts such as understanding what the problem asks of students, what students already know and how that knowledge can be used to overcome difficulties from what students do not know.

Heuristic strategy is an alternative way to solve mathematical problems that aims to optimize students' ability to solve word problems through sequential steps. According to Polya, problem-solving solutions contain four steps: 1) how students correctly understand the problem, 2) how students plan the solution, 3) how students carry out the solution, and 4) how students re-examine the steps taken. This is a common heuristic as a basis for developing a more detailed heuristic model. Wickelgren (1974, in Schoenfeld, 1980) explains Polya's heuristic in more detail, but it still consists of four steps. By going through these steps, learning will be more meaningful because it emphasizes the process, thereby improving students' understanding of the given word problems.

One of the materials that can be used to improve students' mathematical problem-solving abilities is number patterns because the material on number patterns is closely related to everyday life and also to objects in mathematics. In the research of Nukuhaly, et al. (2018) it was revealed that the mathematical objects that students must master are facts, concepts, principles and operations. The ability of 36 students still has great difficulty in solving mathematical problems. Facts in mathematics are related to symbols or symbols, concepts are ideas in classifying a collection of objects, principles are in the form of theorems or properties known in the problem and operations are arrangements of problem solving related to addition, subtraction, multiplication and division (Herdiana, 2019).

Therefore, the researcher is interested in conducting a study entitled “An Analysis of Students’ Ability to Solve Number Pattern Word Problems Based on Their Heuristic Strategies in Junior High School.”

II. RESEARCH METHOD

This research employed a descriptive exploratory method. Descriptive research aims to describe a current event, focusing on the issues that emerged during the research

process. This allows researchers to describe the events as they occurred without assigning any special treatment to them (Mahmud, 2011).

The descriptive method aims to create a systematic, factual, and accurate description or depiction of the facts and characteristics of a particular population or area (Syahza, 2021). In general, the exploratory descriptive method aims to systematically describe the facts and characteristics of a population or area. The object or subject being studied is precisely. In this descriptive research with an exploratory form, what is done is to describe students' ability to solve story problems using number patterns studied from a heuristic strategy.

III. RESULT

The data obtained in this study were in the form of written tests and interviews. The results of the research and discussion in this study were based on data obtained from research conducted at SMP Kemala Bhayangkari 1 Kubu Raya on May 30, 2024. This study aims to determine and describe the ability to solve number pattern story problem exercises studied from heuristic strategies at SMP Kemala Bhayangkari 1 Kubu Raya.

1. Result of the Ability Test for Solving Word Problems mathematical ability test for solving problems on number patterns was given to 36 students. The purpose of the mathematical ability test is to determine students' abilities in understanding problems, planning problems, implementing problems, and drawing conclusions. In this study, the level of students' mathematical problem solving abilities is grouped into three categories, namely high, medium, and low (Azwar, 2012, p. 149). Thus, the grouping of students' mathematical ability levels is categorized into: a) categorization of high problem solving abilities in terms of understanding problems, planning problems, carrying out solution plans and drawing conclusions; b) categorization of medium problem solving abilities in terms of understanding problems, planning problems, carrying out solution plans and drawing conclusions; c) Categorization of low problem solving abilities in terms of understanding problems, planning problems, carrying out solution plans and drawing conclusions.

Table 1. Data on the Mathematical Problem-Solving Ability Scores of Grade VIII Students at SMP Kemala Bhayangkari 1 Kubu Raya.

<i>Nama</i>	<i>Kode Nama</i>	<i>Nilai</i>	<i>Kategori</i>
<i>Affica Shakhira</i>	<i>AS</i>	<i>100</i>	<i>High</i>
<i>Alyssa Chatrien</i>	<i>AC</i>	<i>100</i>	<i>High</i>
<i>Michael</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>100</i>	<i>High</i>
<i>Najla Fakhira Ananti</i>	<i>NFA</i>	<i>100</i>	<i>High</i>
<i>Namira As Siva</i>	<i>NAS</i>	<i>100</i>	<i>High</i>

<i>Ruth Olivia Yolanda Manulang</i>	<i>ROYM</i>	<i>100</i>	<i>High</i>
<i>Zahra Alya Afifah</i>	<i>ZAA</i>	<i>100</i>	<i>High</i>
<i>Dayu Anatasya</i>	<i>DA</i>	<i>84</i>	<i>Currently</i>
<i>Meilani Faradila</i>	<i>MF</i>	<i>84</i>	<i>Currently</i>
<i>Nathania Artanti</i>	<i>NA</i>	<i>84</i>	<i>Currently</i>
<i>Adri Ponsius Firnando</i>	<i>APF</i>	<i>72</i>	<i>Low</i>
<i>Akbar Khadafi</i>	<i>AK</i>	<i>72</i>	<i>Low</i>
<i>Aura Putri Pama</i>	<i>APP</i>	<i>72</i>	<i>Low</i>
<i>Brayen Yordan</i>	<i>BY</i>	<i>72</i>	<i>Low</i>
<i>Fitria Arum Tiftazhani</i>	<i>FAT</i>	<i>72</i>	<i>Low</i>
<i>Hanny Velexsia</i>	<i>HV</i>	<i>72</i>	<i>Low</i>
<i>Jesslyn Alvinna</i>	<i>JA</i>	<i>72</i>	<i>Low</i>
<i>Samuel</i>	<i>S</i>	<i>72</i>	<i>Low</i>
<i>Selamet Ridho</i>	<i>SR</i>	<i>72</i>	<i>Low</i>
<i>Valepi Muhammad Iqbal</i>	<i>VMI</i>	<i>72</i>	<i>Low</i>
<i>Cristian Girtvan</i>	<i>CG</i>	<i>66</i>	<i>Low</i>
<i>Grace Yesa Desipila</i>	<i>GYD</i>	<i>66</i>	<i>Low</i>
<i>Febrianus Riski Tri Saputra</i>	<i>FRTS</i>	<i>44</i>	<i>Low</i>
<i>Florida Agatha</i>	<i>FA</i>	<i>44</i>	<i>Low</i>
<i>Ridho Eka Juliawan</i>	<i>REJ</i>	<i>44</i>	<i>Low</i>
<i>Angel</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>40</i>	<i>Low</i>
<i>Monica Yosephine</i>	<i>MY</i>	<i>40</i>	<i>Low</i>
<i>Chika Christi</i>	<i>CC</i>	<i>38</i>	<i>Low</i>
<i>Mikhael Umbu pada Igo</i>	<i>MUPI</i>	<i>38</i>	<i>Low</i>
<i>Novellino Andrenaliu</i>	<i>NA</i>	<i>38</i>	<i>Low</i>
<i>Rian Marvellino</i>	<i>RM</i>	<i>38</i>	<i>Low</i>
<i>Manuel Ezra</i>	<i>ME</i>	<i>33</i>	<i>Low</i>
<i>Raihan Pratama Adha</i>	<i>RPA</i>	<i>33</i>	<i>Low</i>
<i>Royzi Dizel</i>	<i>RD</i>	<i>33</i>	<i>Low</i>
<i>Febby Violeta</i>	<i>FV</i>	<i>11</i>	<i>Low</i>
<i>Rian Sanjaya Saputra</i>	<i>RSS</i>	<i>11</i>	<i>Low</i>

2. Research Findings

The problem solving indicators used to analyze the results of the subject's work are the result of adaptation of the problem solving ability indicators formulated by Polya (2004) namely understanding the problem includes the subject being able to write down the information contained in the problem and the subject knowing what is asked in the problem; planning a strategy includes the subject being able to determine the formula that will be used to solve the problem; implementing the problem includes the subject being able

Table 2. Analysis of Student’s Mathematical Problem Solving Ability

Step by step Polya	High Category	Medium Category	Low Category
Understanding the Problem	Able to write information that is known and asked very precisely and correctly for all question numbers Able to identify important elements in questions such as the first term and the common difference in an arithmetic sequence	Able to write down known and asked information correctly for all question numbers There is still some confusion. In interpreting information, especially in more complex questions	Difficulty writing known information and asked, especially in question number 3 Unable to identify the first term and common difference in an arithmetic sequence Difficulty in understand the context of story questions related to number patterns
Planning Problem	Able to determine the correct solution steps for all questions Can identify and write appropriate formulas, including sequence and series formulas arithmetic Able to relate known information with relevant mathematical concepts	Able to plan steps to solve most problems Still confused in determine the formula used, especially in question number Difficulty in identifying the correct type of sequence or series for a particular problem	Not yet able to determine a plan clear Unable to write the formula to be used especially in questions 2 and 3 Difficulty in identifying concepts mathematics relevants to the problems
Implementation Problem	Able to do calculations correctly and systematically for all questions Demonstrates clear and structured solutions steps	Can do most calculation s correctly Still making mistakes in mathematical	Difficulty in doing calculations due to not understanding the concepts and steps for solving Make a lot of errors, especially in basic

	Able to apply arithmetic sequence and series formulas correctly	operations, especially multiplication of integers in question number 3 The steps for solving questions 2 and 3 are not systematic enough	mathematical operations Unable to solve some questions, especially numbers 2 and 3
Problem Checking	Able to provide correct and accurate conclusions for all questions Recheck the calculation results Able to interpret calculation results in finding solutions to problem	Can do a recheck, but not thorough enough The conclusion given is still wrong, especially in question number 3 Less able to interpret calculation results in finding solutions to problems	Not yet able to draw conclusions on the problems presented Do not do rechecking the answers given Difficulty in interpreting calculations results to fins solutions to problems

IV. DISCUSSION

1. Problems Solving Ability in Number Pattern Material is Reviewed from Problem Understanding

In the aspect of understanding the problem, students need to identify what is known and asked, what is there, the quantities, relationships and related values and what they are looking for in the given problem.

Students with high problem-solving abilities are able to solve problems correctly. From the solution of these problems, it is clear that students with high problem-solving abilities are able to understand the problem. This is demonstrated by students writing down the known and questioned information in the problem. This finding aligns with the research results of Rofiqoh (2020), which stated that students with high problem-solving abilities are able to understand the problem well and identify the known and questioned information in the problem.

Problems. Yuwono (2019) found in his research that problem-solving ability is a crucial step in the process of solving mathematical problems. Students who are able to understand problems well tend to be more successful in

solving the given mathematical problems. Meanwhile, students with average abilities still experience errors in understanding the problem. Students with low abilities are not yet able to write down the known things in the problem. This is in line with research by Rambe Fauza & Afri (2020) that students with low problem-solving abilities are only able to write down what is known from the problem, but students with low problem-solving abilities are still less able to write down what is asked.

2. Problem Solving Ability in Number Pattern Material is Reviewed from Problem Planning

In the problem planning stage, students think about the steps they will use to find a solution to the problem, apply concepts or what they have learned previously, and apply the solution formulas. Students with high problem-solving skills are able to. They plan problem-solving very well. They can think through the steps to find a solution and apply relevant concepts and theories appropriately. Students with average ability are also able to plan solutions, but still experience errors in determining the concept or formula to be used. Meanwhile, students with low ability have difficulty in planning solutions and are often unable to determine the correct formula or concept. This finding is supported by the results of research by Azizah (2021), which shows that students with high problem-solving ability are able to plan solution strategies well, while students with average and low ability tend to have difficulty in planning appropriate strategies. Rambe Fauza & Afri (2020) in their research also found that students with high problem-solving ability are able to write and explain the solution plan that will be used, students with average ability are not able to write the problem planning process, and students with low problem-solving ability are also not able to write and explain the problem planning process.

3. Problem Solving Ability in Number Pattern Material is Assessed From Problem Implementation

In this indicator, students carry out the plan by entering data, information that has been obtained, performing algorithmic calculations, and paying attention to the calculation steps precisely. Students with high abilities are able to carry out the solution plan very well. They can perform calculations correctly and precisely, and present solutions systematically. Students with average abilities are also able to carry out the solution plan. Meanwhile, students with low abilities have difficulty in carrying out the solution plan and often make errors in calculations. This is in line with the findings of Widodo (2019) which show that students with high problem-solving abilities are able to carry out the solution plan systematically and accurately. Meanwhile, students with average and low abilities tend to have difficulty in carrying out the plan and making accurate calculations. Fauza & Afri (2020) emphasized that students with high problem-solving abilities are more creative in the solution process, students with average abilities more often make errors in the process of implementing problem solving, even students with

average abilities are also mostly unaware of the mistakes they have made, and students with low problem-solving abilities often make errors in the process of implementing the problem, students with low abilities can be seen from the answer sheet more often continue the process of solving from the wrong solution plan.

4. Problem Solving Ability in Number Patterns Material is Reviewed from Re-Checking the Problem

In this indicator, students review their problem understanding, problem planning, and problem implementation with the aim of minimizing or even avoiding errors so they can be corrected. Students with high ability are able to double-check well. They can draw conclusions by writing down the results of the answers or solutions based on the review of the problem correctly and precisely. Students with average ability also double-check, but some of the conclusions obtained are still incorrect. Meanwhile, students with low ability are not yet able to double-check and draw conclusions from the problems presented. This is in line with the findings of Wahyuni (2020), which show that students with high problem-solving abilities tend to double-check the solutions they obtain. Meanwhile, students with medium and low abilities often neglect this stage, which can lead to errors in their conclusions. Fauza & Afri (2020) explain that students with high problem-solving abilities are able to write down the final results they have obtained by providing reinforcing statements. They always check and review the answers they have completed. Students with moderate abilities also sometimes recheck, and students with low problem-solving abilities very rarely recheck.

V. CONCLUSION

Based on the results of research and analysis on each indicator reviewed from problem understanding, problem planning, problem implementation and re-checking of problems with high, medium and low ability categories, it was found that there were significant differences in the ability to solve story problem exercises on number pattern material in each category, especially in terms of problem understanding, problem solving planning, solution implementation and re-checking of solution results, so it can be concluded that: (1) Students with high problem understanding ability are able to understand problems well, students write down information that is known and asked, students with medium problem solving ability are able to understand problems well, students write down information that is known and asked, and students with low problem understanding ability have not been able to understand problems well, students still have difficulty in writing down information that is known and asked in the problem. (2) Students with high problem planning ability

are able to make a very good solution plan and can formulate the right strategy to solve problems, students with low ability still have errors in determining the solution plan and making a solution plan for complex problems, and

students with low problem solving ability have not been able to make a proper and correct solution plan, so they have difficulty in formulating problem solving. (3) Students with high problem solving plan implementation abilities are able to carry out the solution very well, can use the formulas that have been determined in the solution plan and carry out calculations precisely and correctly, students with moderate problem solving abilities still have errors in calculations when carrying out the solution and the solutions obtained are sometimes inaccurate due to errors in the calculation process (calculations), and students with low problem solving abilities experience difficulties in carrying out the problem solving plan because they are not yet able to determine and use formulas, and make errors in the calculation process (4) Students recheck the problem where students with high problem solving abilities are able to draw conclusions from the problem precisely and correctly and students with high problem solving abilities always recheck the results of the problem solving, students with moderate problem solving abilities can draw conclusions but in some complex problems the conclusions obtained are wrong and students with moderate problem solving abilities may recheck, but are unable to identify errors in calculations and students with low problem solving abilities are unable to recheck the results of the solutions they obtain and are unable to draw conclusions because they do not obtain a solution to the problem presented

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